

**ASSESSING THE INFLUENCE OF CULTURAL CONTEXT ON RESEARCH
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ABSTRACT

Cultural context played a significant role in shaping research methodologies. This study described and examined teachers' perceptions on the key factors influencing research method selection. It employed a descriptive correlational research design. It was participated by 200 randomly selected public secondary school teachers in the Philippines. Results showed that cultural values and beliefs were highly perceived by teachers as the most significant element influencing research methods selection followed by communication style and access to resources. On the other hand, teachers frequently encountered that cultural misunderstanding, access to participants and language barriers were significant challenges encountered surrounding cultural context in research methodologies selection. Apparently, there was a positive correlation between cultural contexts in terms of cultural values and beliefs in selecting research methodologies and the challenges encountered by teachers in terms of cultural misunderstanding which suggested while aligning methodologies with cultural values, it was equally critical to address the potential misunderstanding occurred in selecting proper research methodologies.

Keywords:

Assess, influence, cultural, context, research, method, values, beliefs, misunderstanding

INTRODUCTION

In the conduct of educational researches in the Philippines is one of the critical aspect in scholarly writing. The Philippine as a nation holds diverse culture exhibiting precolonial culture to colonial culture. Aside from this, the Philippines also possess diverse people who characterize different perceptions, behavior and values. Along this differences, still Filipinos from sectors of society one shared culture which is the core identity of the Filipinos—resilient and compassionate. On one hand, the conduct of scholarly writings such as academic researches commonly focused on diverse disciplines where researchers opted to select different groups of respondents in a single research study. In view of culture, Filipinos from different disciplines have diverse perspectives and behavior which makes more interesting for researchers to explore such. In doing research, one of the primary considerations is the familiarity on the orientations, characteristics and demographics of targeted-respondents. When researchers craft their researches, they usually observe the prevailing conditions surfacing the societal landscape and relate the same in their disciplines. Foremost critical consideration also involve the proper understanding on the cultural context of the targeted respondents although they share similar culture but because of the demographic and geographic factors their traditions, beliefs and other practices are different from one another. In this regard, understanding the influence of cultural context on the proper selection of research

method is of paramount importance because it is crucial for conducting effective and ethically-responsive research. In addition, cultural factors may shape the way research is designed, implemented and interpreted. While, it is imperative to emphasize the cultural context of researchers' targeted respondents when selecting research methods and they are also expected to understand different cultures which may vary from region to region. Accordingly, the researchers observed that most of teacher-researchers abruptly selected their research methods when conducting educational researches. This causes serious concerns as collectively deduced by the researchers based on their observations on the basis that ethical protocols and culture-sensitive data collection procedure may also affected either positively or negatively. Apart from this observations, the researchers also observed that most teacher-researchers are only selecting research methods based on their research works' objective but failing to logically examine if there are prevailing cultural practices and norms to be considered when formulating such designed research topics. So these conditions ignited the researchers' interest to comprehensively assess the influence of cultural context on research method selection.

There is a methodological gap that can be filled by qualitative approach in cross-cultural research as well as in consideration in selecting culture-based research methods. Means-end methodology offer significant strengths and addressing several levels of weaknesses of the culture-based research method selection (Watkins, 2010). Cross-cultural research requires a keen eye for rigorous methodology in such research. Appreciation that methodological aspects of such studies underscore the importance of acknowledging and recognizing the prevailing culture. A careful design and analysis can help build a strong cultural consideration in conducting research works (He & Vijver, 2017). In addition, psychological and educational assessments are considered for reducing bias specifically by assessing cultural variables and threats to the validity of research methods as aligned with the prevailing cultural contexts of the research's participants (Ramlackhan, 2023). There are critical aspects in addressing scientifically culture-based research methods selections which included the ability to harness culture-centered knowledge and perspectives from communities, utilization of indigenous-based theories and cultural adaptation mechanisms (Dickerson et al., 2018). Focusing on the cultural context, it enabled the researchers to understand and familiarize with their participants' mindset, perceptions and behaviors. Cultural context commonly shapes a research encounter thereby, affecting the validity and accuracy of research findings (Bayeck, 2021). In this line, the researchers establish a strong knowledge gap based on the cited previous studies since these studies only focused on the culture-based considerations of the different countries, there are less number of researches published with regard to assessing the influence of cultural context in research methods selection in the Philippines. So, this present study fills this gap. Apparently, significance of the study lies in the provision of scientific evidence based on the teachers perceptions on the influence of cultural context in research methods selections among researches locally administered in the Philippines. In addition, this study supports SDG 4 (Quality Education) since the study may provide logical baseline and data about the perceptions of teachers on the influence of cultural context in selecting research methods. As such, the data and the scientific analyses contained in this paper may be used for the formulation or modification of institutional research standards of basic and higher education institutions to yield a more comprehensive and culture-based research.

OBJECTIVES

This study assessed the influence of cultural context on research method selection based on the perceptions of public secondary schools in the Philippines. It specifically answered the following:

1. How may teachers' perceptions on the cultural elements influencing research methods selection be assessed in terms of:
 - 1.1 values and beliefs;
 - 1.2 communication and styles; and
 - 1.3 access to resources?
2. What are the challenges encountered by the teachers in using cultural context in research methods selection in terms of:
 - 2.1 understanding culture;
 - 2.2 access to participants; and
 - 2.3 linguistic aspect?

3. Is there a significant relationship between the cultural contexts influencing teachers' research methods selection and the challenges they encountered?

Hypothesis:

The study hypothesized that there is no significant relationship between the cultural contexts influencing teachers' research methods selection and the challenges they encountered.

METHODOLOGY

The study employed a descriptive correlational research design in order to assess the influence of cultural context on research method selection. Thus, the researchers used a simple random sampling to select the participation of 200 public secondary school teachers among the selected schools in the Philippines. On the other hand, researchers used a researcher-made survey-questionnaire which was subjected to validation and reliability testing through pilot test. For the construction of the survey-questionnaire, part 1 of the instrument contained items relating to the teachers' perceptions on the cultural elements influencing research methods selection while part 2 contained items relating to the challenges encountered by teachers in using cultural context in research methods selection. On one hand, validation was made through the expertise of three (3) professionals holding a doctorate degree in educational management and supervision. Then, the researchers complied with the recommendations to enhance or modify the developed instrument, the researchers proceeded to pilot testing where they conducted it among non-included respondents. Results of the reliability test showed that items under part 1, obtained a Cronbach Alpha result of .712 while items under part 2, gained a Cronbach Alpha result of .872, both described as "acceptable." Further, the researchers used google forms in administering their survey-questionnaire. They were able to send the link to the respondents' personal email addresses. Once all the data have been collected, the researchers organized the gathered raw data using MS Excel. As to the data analysis, the researchers used mean, standard deviation and general weighted mean in order to examine teachers' perceptions on the cultural elements influencing research methods selection and the challenges encountered by the respondents in using cultural context for research methods selection. Also, the researchers used Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) in order to examine if there would be significant relationship between the cultural contexts influencing teachers' research methods selection and the challenges they encountered. And, informed consent and short briefing were used as ethical protocols before the actual administration of the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Assessing the influence of cultural context on research method selection is of significant value in the spheres of research and development. In the Philippines, a nation endowed with rich tapestry of cultural traditions and values serve as microcosms of the diversity which is commonly subject of serious considerations. Understanding also the interplay of cultural factors and research methods selection, pose critical contributions in the research as a discipline on the basis that it could provide accurate insights and meaningful findings derived from accurate data sources and highly aligned methods.

1. **Perceptions on the Cultural Elements Influencing Research Methods Selection.** The results showed that values and beliefs obtained the highest mean score of 3.81, described as highly perceived while communication and styles gained a closely relative mean score of 3.79, described as highly perceived. Thus, access to resources variable gained a mean score of 3.61, also described as highly perceived. The results implied that teachers highly perceived values and beliefs as the most influential as cultural element in research methods selection. This implied the importance of understanding cultural context which may significantly shape participants responses and engagement. On one hand, communication and styles are also highly perceived by the teachers which indicated that researchers were opted to adapt their communication styles to align with the prevailing cultural norms of their respondents. Thus, the result implied that effective communication which included use of local dialects and culturally appropriate dialogues could pose trust and improve data quality. Lastly, access to resources are also viewed as highly perceived cultural element emphasizing its influence on research methods selection indicating the recognition of significant role in accessing educational plays, practices and the like that enabled the researcher build proper and relevant research methods. Results of the study supported the study of Truong and Hallinger (2017) which claimed that observed patterns of

cultural contexts influenced the researchers' choices in research methods selection. Also, similar study revealed that understanding culture was central player in providing accurate and reliable research findings.

2. **Challenges Encountered by the Teachers in Using Cultural Context in Research Methods Selection.** The results showed that understanding culture gained the highest mean score of 3.67, described as always encountered while access to participants gained a mean score of 3.51, also described as always encountered. Also, the results showed that linguistic aspect obtained a mean score of 3.47, described as always encountered. The results implied that teachers always encountered cultural misunderstanding. This also suggested that a deep comprehension of cultural nuances was essential but often difficult to achieve. Understanding culture involved the recognition of values and beliefs of a group where in the context of research selection method, teacher-researchers frequently struggle with this because of varying level of cultural awareness. On one hand, the result on access to participants, it indicated that teacher-researchers were significantly challenged in the selection and participation of their targeted respondents coming from diverse cultural backgrounds. In line with this, accessing the participants specifically in communities where culture and traditions. were valued deeply. Locals appreciation to outsiders like the researchers who were conducting their studies, frequently encountered skepticism. Lastly, the results signified that teachers always struggled language barriers in which difficulties in communities with the targeted respondents occurred. This posed significant challenge for teacher-researchers to efficiently convey their intent and interests as they conducted their studies or planned to choose a proper research method. Apparently, language differences created significant barriers in data collection and interpretation forming a defective part of their research methods selection as well as implementation. Results of the study supported the study of Pelzaang and Hutchinson (2018) which revealed that traditional cultural values and customs significantly raised challenge and barrier for researchers in selecting and implementing their research method. Similar study also showed that researchers were commonly confronted with intercultural perceptions making it difficult to engage culturally-rooted participants.
3. **Relationship Between Cultural Context Influencing Teachers' Research Methods Selection and The Challenges They Encountered.** The results showed that there was a positive correlation between cultural contexts in terms of cultural values and beliefs and the challenges encountered by teachers in terms of cultural misunderstanding (understanding of culture) with correlation coefficient result of $r=.489$. Thus, the null hypothesis, "There is no significant relationship between the cultural contexts influencing teachers' research methods selection and the challenges they encountered," was rejected. This suggested that while aligning methodologies with cultural values, it was equally critical to address the potential misunderstanding occurred in selecting proper research methodologies. Further, the results signified that cultural values and beliefs of teacher-researchers may simultaneously experience greater difficulty in fully understanding different cultural nuances. Results of the study supported the study of Katitas et al. (2024) which revealed that intercultural sensitivity plays a crucial role in the relationship between cultural intelligence, culture-based studies and multicultural education including research and other scholarly works. Thus, the study implicated that there was a need for comprehensive cultural training to be conveyed and explored not only surface-level understanding but also deep engagement with cultural dynamics.

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CONCLUSION

The conduct of scholarly writings such as academic researches commonly focused on diverse disciplines where researchers opted to select different groups of respondents in a single research study. Cultural values and beliefs

were highly perceived by teachers as the most significant element influencing research methods selection followed by communication style and access to resources. On the other hand, teachers frequently encountered that cultural misunderstanding, access to participants and language barriers were significant challenges encountered surrounding cultural context in research methodologies selection. Apparently, there was a positive correlation between cultural contexts in terms of cultural values and beliefs in selecting research methodologies and the challenges encountered by teachers in terms of cultural misunderstanding which suggested while aligning methodologies with cultural values, it was equally critical to address the potential misunderstanding occurred in selecting proper research methodologies.

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